

Satisfaction on Affiliation and Skills Enhancement Among University of Mindanao College of Hospitality Education Pastry Club Members

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Abstract: *The study aimed to determine the level of satisfaction on affiliation and skills enhancement of 150 University of Mindanao-College of Hospitality Education Pastry Club Members. This study employed non-experimental design utilizing descriptive survey method technique. The statistical used were mean, and Pearson r. The level of satisfaction on Affiliation and Skills Enhancement among CHE Pastry Club Members concerning academic experience, social experience and overall experience were found to be very satisfied. Whilst the level of skills enhancement in terms of Creativity and Management among CHE Pastry Club Members were very satisfied. Using Pearson r, results concluded that there is a substantial relationship between affiliation and skills enhancement, which leads to accepting the null hypothesis Affiliation and Skills Enhancement among CHE Pastry Club Members. This means that affiliation satisfaction affects the acquiring skills assessment among the Pastry club members. This will enable the members to gain a more competitive edge in striving to learn and develop, which will prepare them for the real industry. This can be concluded that the higher involvement of the students in clubs and organizations will provide more significant opportunities in achieving advantageous development of success. Furthermore, participative students in every activity will have high satisfaction, which leads to developed and enhanced skills. It will strengthen the leadership skills that would be advantageous to all management students*

Keywords: *Satisfaction, Affiliation, Skills Enhancement, Pastry Club Members*

I. INTRODUCTION

One of the objectives of advanced education is to get ready understudies for their calling or occupation. Notwithstanding the customary classroom condition, different open doors can help understudies advance their expert advantages and create proficient aptitudes (Patterson, 2012). Inclusion in understudy associations is considered one of those open doors for expertise improvement. Foubert and Urbanski (2006) have detailed that increasingly included understudies have more noteworthy aptitude advancement than uninvolved understudies that bring down formative scores.

As characterized by the English Webster lexicon, inclusion is any action outside the schoolroom that might upgrade and increase understudy learning. Astin (1984) also described understudy inclusion as a measure of physical vitality understudies apply and the action of mental vitality, they put into their school understanding. Being included, being over-included, or not being included at all in extracurricular exercises and how investment can affect what is the fate of the understudies later on dependent on interest in practices (Wilson, 2009). By and large, understudy associations give people the chance to gain or create esteemed aptitudes. The involvement of student clubs and organizations has undoubtedly benefited students in all aspects. Still, there are factors such as the management skills, implementation, and efficiency of the club facilitators or officials considered by the researchers in this study. Besides, many student club facilitators appear not to have a role in managing these extracurricular activities. Aquino, Russell, Cutrona and Altmeir (1996) stated that facilitators should also have their roles to play to manage and supervise extracurricular activities to work. As the organization's operation and ways in which it can pursue its mission continue to expand, the governance responsibilities and tasks will increase (Smith and Shen, 1996). Consequently, the number of duties will also increase if the task specialization in the governing body increases, which means the officers can be Irresponsible and inefficient. However, due to unplanned and unorganized activities carried out by the officers, members of student-based organizations may not be satisfied with their association (Larupay and Lanut,2010).

Besides, the researchers noted that the students, in particular, are associated with the College of Hospitality Education. (CHE) will not give importance to joining clubs due to certain factors of the skills of the officers and the proper implementation of the activities of the organizations. Because of the studies mentioned above and citations, the researchers would like to see whether or not there is a relationship between satisfaction with affiliation and skills improvement among club members; and distinguish if there are significant differences between the level of affiliation satisfaction and the development of skills. Given the current situation, researchers were encouraged to carry out a study in comfort on affiliation and skills enhancement among UM CHE Pastry Club members.

The study aims to determine satisfaction with affiliation and skills enhancement among CHE Pastry Club members. Specifically, the study sought to answer the following questions: (1) What is the level of satisfaction in Pastry Club members in terms of Academic Experience, Social Experience; and Overall Experience?; (2) What is the members' level of skills enhancement in terms of: Creativity; and Management?; and Is there a significant relationship between satisfaction with affiliation and skills enhancement among CHE Pastry Club members?.

II. REVIEW RELATED LITERATURE

Satisfaction on Affiliation

Satisfaction is an evaluation of emotion, which reflects how a participant believes that their use of the service evoked positive feelings towards the program (Cronin, Brady, & Hult, 2000). Murray and Howat (2002) study explained service quality as a fundamental mechanism for behavioral intentions. Providing a service that satisfies customers will generally improve profitability for any organization that operates in a consumer market. The study also stated that customers' satisfaction was positively related to their willingness to recommend the service, leading to more students participating (Murray & Howat, 2002). With the same concept, Reynolds (2016) used this model in his study entitled "Participation and Commitment to Intramural and Club Sports with Students' Intention to Return to Campus." Which can directly be applied to the intramural and club sports program as it is a customer service entity at a university relying on its customers (i.e., the student) to return to school. The result indicates that commitment and satisfaction levels significantly affected the student's intention to return to campus.

Academic and Skills Enhancement

Students have a more significant opportunity to grow and learn about the globe. The coed organization is one such chance given to students to be told and enhance skills. College clubs may offer many positive benefits to students. Some of the benefits are the chance for college students to be highly organized, skilled in group development, and excellent time management skills with multiple commitments (Wilson & Zhang, 2009). Gardner's theory of multiple intelligences in 1993 broadens our view of how humans learn and realize their potential. This theory explains how various skills and talents help strengthen an individual, so students need to be exposed to various activities to explore their interests and capabilities. For instance, in the Philippines, a research study conducted by Olayan, Caranto and David (2015) examined the results of structure activities to the teachers and social functioning of student nurses of Benguet State University from a phenomenological purpose of reading four nursing student leaders. The result expressed that students' activities conducted during their establishment function as AN avenue to reinforce their nursing skills, leadership skills, relationship skills, technical skills, language and communication skills, and prioritization and management skills.

III. METHOD

The researchers used the descriptive design and applied using a survey questionnaire and critical informant interview. The survey provided structured questionnaires to several identified respondents from the colleges inside the University of Mindanao Matina Campus. The participants who were asked to evaluate their Satisfaction with Affiliation and Skills Enhancement among Pastry Club during the survey were randomly selected from identified respondents. The study was aided using an interview guide questionnaire.

The study participants refer to the University of Mindanao students from the Pastry Club organizational club in the College of Hospitality Education. The researchers aim to collect data from the respondents using our made questionnaires. There were expected to be 150 members of the pastry club, 20% are new members, and 80% are old where the data will be taken. The response of the participants well carefully considered. The study's independent and dependent variable will be scaled using a 5-level Likert scaling system.

The steps followed by the researchers in the gathering of data are as follows: (1) Seeking Permission to Conduct the Study. The researchers furnished a letter of permission, which has been approved by the Research Coordinator and Panelists, to collect data and information regarding satisfaction on affiliation and skills enhancement among UM CHE Pastry Club; (2) Collection of Data and Information. Upon approval, the researchers distributed the survey questionnaires to the selected student in the Organizational Pastry Club at the University of Mindanao Matina Campus; and (3) Retrieval of Data and Information. The researchers retrieved the data information, and the gathered data was tallied, analyzed, and subjected to statistical analysis.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section manifested the interpretation and analysis of the findings of the study. Discussions of the topics are presented based on the following subheadings: Level of satisfaction on affiliation and skills enhancement among CHE Pastry Club members; the significant difference in the level of satisfaction on affiliation and skills enhancement among CHE Pastry Club members when analyzed by age, sex, status, and year level.

Level of Satisfaction on Affiliation and Skills Enhancement among CHE Pastry Club Members

Table 1 presents the level of satisfaction with affiliation with Pastry Club members of the University of Mindanao. The result shows that the overall experience got the highest level of satisfaction with an average score of 4.40, followed by Academic Experience (4.36) and Social Experience (4.36). This means that the student of the BSHRM program of the University of Mindanao under the Pastry Club members was generally delighted with their overall experience in participating in the club's activities with a great balance of satisfaction between their academic and social experience. They perceived the importance of the programs that the college has been offered through the wide range of skills it imparts to the members, such as time management and multi-tasking and the cooperation of the professors. Furthermore, students with high satisfaction with the overall experience with academically and socially performing and active will be able to obtain affirmative outcomes towards intellectual development and personal growth. These indicate that students were able to learn how they allocate their time effectively in their daily school routine and balance it between their curricular and non-curricular activities. The support they get from the instructors draws them to engage more in the club activities.

Table 1. *Level of Satisfaction on Affiliation and Skills Enhancement among CHE Pastry Club Members*

Indicators	Mean	Std. Deviation	Descriptive Level
Academic Experience	4.36	0.541	Very Satisfied
Social Experience	4.36	0.544	Very Satisfied
Overall Experience	4.40	0.496	Very Satisfied
Overall	4.37	0.479	Very Satisfied

Moreover, the research findings inferred a positive response regarding the members' social experience within the organization. They were able to obtain more friends having an interest the same as they are and a friendly relationship with the club's mentors as; they play a key role in the students' participation (Webber, Krylow, & Zhang, 2013). The Aspen Institution (2018) found out that multiple instructional strategies can support students' social and emotional development, including opportunities such as project-based learning, academic activities, non-academic activities, and internships that require students to practice develop their skills and knowledge. Through these approaches, students will obtain opportunities to explicitly learn, which helps develop and improve their academic performance and is often the first step for educators seeking to comprehensively support their students.

Level of Skills Enhancement in terms of Creativity and Management among CHE Pastry Club Members

Table 2 shows the skills enhancement of the CHE Pastry club members towards creativity and management. Based on the result, the overall mean score of 4.34 and both indicators, management and creativity, similarly obtained a mean rating of 4.34. It shows that pastry club members are very satisfied with how the club officers manage and facilitate the club in terms of activities and events, which may also refer to the competency enhancement program that the club is conducting. In addition, the creativity that the club possesses towards the club activities satisfies the members. This is through the series of topics presented relating to pastry skills- baking, dressing the cake, etc. Therefore, well collaboration of excellent facilitators of the club and the continuous generating of innovative ideas will enable the

pursuit of a high level of satisfaction, and an increase of interest will be manifested towards the members to involve themselves in the club further.

Table 2. Level of skills enhancement among CHE Pastry Club members

Indicators	Mean	Std. Deviation	Descriptive Level
Management	4.34	0.605	Very Satisfied
Creativity	4.34	0.591	Very Satisfied
Overall	4.34	0.583	Very Satisfied

Therefore, competencies square measure a vital determinant of the effectiveness and potency of the leader’s work. There is square measure a mirrored image of the extent of skilled tasks. Up to date, they're characterized by variability in time and, Therefore, Development. Moreover, they're additionally measurable- that is why they ought to be subjected to a scientific assessment. Presently gained data and knowledge doesn't guarantee success within the geographical point for leaders.

Significant Relationship between Satisfaction on Affiliation and Skills Enhancement among CHE Pastry Club Members

Table 4 shows the significant relationship of the CHE Pastry Club between satisfaction and skills enhancement. Results concluded that there is a substantial relationship between affiliation and skills enhancement, which leads to accepting the null hypothesis.

Table 4. Correlation between satisfaction on affiliation and skills enhancement among CHE Pastry Club members

Variables Correlated	r-value	Verbal Description	df (n-2)	p-value	Decision
Satisfaction on Affiliation vs Skills Enhancement	0.037	No Relationship	98	0.005	Ho is accepted

Legend: * Correlation is significant at 0.01 level (2-tailed)

This means that affiliation satisfaction affects the acquiring skills assessment among the Pastry club members. This will enable the members to gain a more competitive edge in striving to learn and develop, which will prepare them for the real industry. This can be concluded that the higher involvement of the students in clubs and organizations will provide more significant opportunities in achieving advantageous development of success. Furthermore, participative students in every activity will have high satisfaction, which leads to developed and enhanced skills. It will strengthen the leadership skills that would be advantageous to all management students (Smith & Chenoweth, 2015). The study of Dhaqane and Afrah (2016) resulted in a significant relationship between academic performance and satisfaction, as well as the other factors that contribute to academic performance. The study found that satisfaction promotes both academic achievement and retention of the student.

V. CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions are drawn:

1. In determining the level satisfaction on affiliation in Pastry Club members of the University of Mindanao were satisfied. This means that Pastry club members were generally very satisfied with their overall experience in participating the activities of the club with well balance satisfaction between their academic and social experience.
2. The level of skills enhancement in creativity and management among CHE pastry club members were very satisfied. Thus, members were generally very satisfied regarding on the club officers on how they facilitate the club and the creativity that the club possesses in terms of series of activities and events which may refer to the

competency enhancement program that the club is conducting.

3. The study revealed no significant relationship between affiliation and skills enhancement.

VI. RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings and conclusions of this study, the following recommendations are offered:

1. Pastry club management might further extend their efforts and support and the college and club mentors to attain the highest possible satisfaction regarding mentoring the members to impart them a competitive edge among others in the field of pastry assessment.
2. The college program might review the club's effectiveness in the actual industry setting to improve and also strategies on how the students will be able to put their interest in performing such skill.
3. Future researchers might further improve the study by assessing not only one college club to evaluate the effectiveness of the organization and how it affects their interest in their chosen career in the future.

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